

Haar wavelet method for solving FitzHugh-Nagumo equation

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Abstract—In this paper, we develop an accurate and efficient Haar wavelet method for well-known FitzHugh-Nagumo equation. The proposed scheme can be used to a wide class of nonlinear reaction-diffusion equations. The power of this manageable method is confirmed. Moreover the use of Haar wavelets is found to be accurate, simple, fast, flexible, convenient, small computation costs and computationally attractive.

Keywords—FitzHugh-Nagumo equation; Haar wavelet method; Adomain decomposition method; Computationally attractive.

I. INTRODUCTION

The nonlinear equation proposed by Hodgkin and Huxley [13] is the most widely accepted mathematical description of the excitation and propagation of nerve impulses [3,9,21,28], that is

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + u(u - \alpha)(1 - u) \quad (1)$$

where α is an arbitrary constant. This generally called FitzHugh-Nagumo (FN) equation. The FN system of equations has been derived by both FitzHugh [8] and Nagumo et al. [22]. It is an important nonlinear reaction-diffusion equation used in circuit theory, biology and the area of population genetics [4] as mathematical models. The FN equation describes the dynamical behavior near the bifurcation point for the Rayleigh-Benard convection of binary fluid mixtures [24]. When $\alpha = 1$, the FN equation reduces to the real Newell-Whitehead equation. By using Hirota method, Kawahara and Tanaka [16] have found new exact solutions of Eq. (1); by applying the non-classical symmetry reductions approach, Nucci and Clarkson [23] have obtained some new exact solutions with Jacobbi elliptic function. Some other solutions of Eq. (1) have been given by several authors [6,25,27]. Huaying Li and Yucui Guo [20] have obtained the new exact solutions of the FN equation by using first integral method. More recently, Abbasbandy [1] proposed the Soliton solutions for the FN equation by using homotopy analysis method. Abdusalam [2] studied the Analytic and approximate solutions for Nagumo telegraph reaction diffusion equation. Angela Slavova and Pietro Zecca [26] have introduced a cellular neural network (CNN) model of FN equation. In this paper, we develop Haar wavelet method for solving Eq. (1). In solving ordinary differential equations by using Haar wavelet related method, Chen and Hsiao [7] had derived an operational matrix of integration

based on Haar wavelet. Lepik [17,18,19] had solved higher order as well as nonlinear ODEs and some nonlinear evolution equations by Haar wavelet method. Hariharan et al. [11] have introduced a Haar wavelet method for solving Fisher's equation. We introduce a Haar wavelet method for solving the FitzHugh-Nagumo (FN) equation with the initial and boundary conditions, which will exhibit several advantageous features: i) Very high accuracy fast transformation and possibility of implementation of fast algorithms compared with other known methods. ii) The simplicity and small computation costs, resulting from the sparsity of the transform matrices and the small number of significant wavelet coefficients. iii) The method is also very convenient for solving the boundary value problems, since the boundary conditions are taken care of automatically. Beginning from 1980's, wavelets have been used for solution of partial differential equations (PDE). The good features of this approach are possibility to detect singularities, irregular structure and transient phenomena exhibited by the analyzed equations. Most of the wavelet algorithms can handle exactly periodic boundary conditions. The wavelet algorithms for solving PDE are based on the Galerkin techniques or on the collocation method. Evidently all attempts to simplify the wavelet solutions for PDE are welcome. One possibility for this is to make use of the Haar wavelet family. Haar wavelets (which are Daubechies of order 1) consists of piecewise constant functions and are therefore the simplest orthonormal wavelets with a compact support. A drawback of the Haar wavelets is their discontinuity. Since the derivatives do not exist in the breaking points it is not possible to apply the Haar wavelets for solving PDE directly. There are two possibilities for getting out of this situation. One way is to regularize the Haar wavelets with interpolating splines (e.g. B-splines or Deslaurier-Dabuc interpolating wavelets). This approach has been applied by Cattani [5], but the regularization process considerably complicates the solution and the main advantage of the Haar wavelets—the simplicity gets to some extent lost. The other way is to make use of the integral method, which was proposed by Chen and Hsiao [7]. There are discussions by other researchers [12,14]. The paper is organized the following way. For completeness sake the Haar wavelet method is presented in Section 2. Function approximation is presented in Section 3. The method of solution of the FitzHugh-Nagumo (FN) equation is proposed in Section 4. Some numerical examples are presented in Section 5. Concluding remarks are given in Section 6.

II. HAAR WAVELET PRELIMINARIES

Haar wavelet is the simplest wavelet. Haar transform or Haar wavelet transform has been used as an earliest example

for orthonormal wavelet transform with compact support. The Haar wavelet transform is the first known wavelet and was proposed in 1910 by Alfred Haar. They are step functions (piecewise constant functions) on the real line that can take only three values. Haar wavelets, like the well-known Walsh functions (Rao 1983), form an orthogonal and complete set of functions representing discretized functions and piecewise constant functions. A function is said to be piecewise constant if it is locally constant in connected regions.

The Haar transform is one of the earliest examples of what is known now as a compact, dyadic, orthonormal wavelet transform. The Haar function, being an odd rectangular pulse pair, is the simplest and oldest orthonormal wavelet with compact support. In the mean time, several definitions of the Haar functions and various generalizations have been published and used. They were intended to adopt this concept to some practical applications as well as to extend its in applications to different classes of signals. Haar functions appear very attractive in many applications as for example, image coding, edge extraction, and binary logic design.

After discretizing the differential equations in a conventional way like the finite difference approximation, wavelets can be used for algebraic manipulations in the system of equations obtained which lead to better condition number of the resulting system.

The previous work in system analysis via Haar wavelets was led by Chen and Hsiao [6], who first derived a Haar operational matrix for the integrals of the Haar function vector and put the application for the Haar analysis into the dynamical systems. Then, the pioneer work in state analysis of linear time delayed systems via Haar wavelets was laid down by Hsiao [10], who first proposed a Haar product matrix and a coefficient matrix. Hsiao and Wang proposed a key idea to transform the time-varying function and its product with states into a Haar product matrix. The orthogonal set of Haar function is shown in Fig.1. This is a group of square waves with magnitudes of in certain intervals and zeros elsewhere. For applications of the Haar transform in logic design, efficient ways of calculating the Haar spectrum from reduced forms of Boolean functions are needed.

The Haar wavelet family for is defined as follows.

$$h_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } t \in \left[\frac{k}{m}, \frac{k+0.5}{m}\right) \\ -1 & \text{for } t \in \left[\frac{k+0.5}{m}, \frac{k+1}{m}\right) \\ 0 & \text{, elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Integer $m = 2^j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, J$) indicates the level of the wavelet; $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1$ is the translation parameter. Maximal level of resolution is J . The index i is calculated according to the formula $i = m + k + 1$; in the case of minimal values $m=1, k=0$, we have $i=2$, the maximal value of i is $2^m = 2^{(J+1)}$. It is assumed that the value $i=1$ corresponds to the scaling function for which h_{-1} . Let us define the collocation points and discretise the Haar function in this way we get the coefficient matrix, which has the dimension. The operational matrix of integration P , which is a $2M$ square matrix, is defined by the equation

$$(PH)_{il} = \int_0^{t_l} h_i(t) dt \quad (3)$$

Any function $y(t)$ which is square integrable in the interval $[0, 1)$ can be expanded in a Haar series with an infinite number of terms $y(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i h_i(t)$, $i = 2^j + k$, $j \geq 0, 0 \leq k < 2^j$, $t \in [0, 1)$

where the Haar coefficients

$$c_i = 2^j \int_0^1 y(t) h_i(t) dt$$

are determined in such a way that the integral square error

$$E = \int_0^1 \left[y(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} c_i h_i(t) \right]^2 dt$$

is minimum where $m = 2^j$, $j \in \{0\} \cup N$

In general, for the function $y(t)$ to be smooth the series expansion in equation (3) contains an infinite number of terms. If $y(t)$ is a piecewise constant or may be approximated as piecewise constants, then the sum in equation (4) will be terminated after m terms, that is

$$y(t) \cong \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} c_i h_i(t) = c_m^T h_m(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } t \in [0, 1) \text{ and } c_m \triangleq [c_0, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{m-1}]^T \quad (5)$$

where T stands for transposition, m stands for their dimension.

The first four Haar functions can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} h_0(t) &= [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1] \\ h_1(t) &= [1 \ 1 \ -1 \ -1] \\ h_2(t) &= [1 \ -1 \ 0 \ 0] \\ h_3(t) &= [0 \ 0 \ 1 \ -1] \end{aligned}$$

If $y(t) = [7 \ 1 \ 3 \ 0]$ is piecewise constant then, $y(t) = \frac{11}{4}h_0(t) + \frac{5}{4}h_1(t) + 3h_2(t) + \frac{3}{2}h_3(t) = c^T H(t)$ where

$$H(t) = H_4(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} h_0(t) \\ h_1(t) \\ h_2(t) \\ h_3(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The Haar coefficients c_i can be obtained by using (5) directly. c_i can also be obtained by matrix inversion. For this piecewise constant $y(t)$,

$$c^T = y(t) H_4^{-1} = \left[\frac{11}{4} \quad \frac{5}{4} \quad 3 \quad \frac{3}{2} \right]$$

Equation (12) is called forward transform that is used to obtain wavelet coefficients. The function $y(t)$ can be recovered from the corresponding wavelet coefficients and the wavelets $h_i(t)$. Hence (10) is known as inverse transform. As H and H^{-1} contain many zeros, this phenomenon makes the Haar transform much faster than the Fourier and Walsh transforms.

A. Integration of Haar wavelets:

In wavelet analysis for a dynamical system, all functions need to be transformed into Haar series. As impulse functions are not preferred (since they are the derivatives of Haar wavelets), integration of Haar wavelets are preferred, which is expanded into Haar series with coefficient matrix P [15].

$\int_0^1 h_m(t)dt \cong P_{m \times m} h_m(t)$, $t \in [0, 1]$ Where $m \times m$ square matrix P is called the operational matrix of integration which satisfies the following recursive formula.

$$P_{1 \times 1} = \left\langle \frac{1}{2} \right\rangle P_{m \times m} = \frac{1}{2m} \begin{bmatrix} 2m P_{\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}} & -H_{\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}} \\ H_{\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}}^{-1} & O_{\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where $O_{\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}}$ is a null matrix of order $\frac{m}{2} \times \frac{m}{2}$
 $H_{m \times m} \triangleq [h_m(t_0) \ h_m(t_1) \ \dots \ h_m(t_{m-1})]$
 and

$$\frac{i}{m} \leq t < i + \frac{1}{m} \text{ and } H_{m \times m}^{-1} = \frac{1}{m} H_{m \times m}^T \text{diag}(r)$$

$$r \triangleq \left[\begin{array}{cccccccc} 1 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 4 & 4 & 4 & 4 & \dots & \dots & \underbrace{\frac{m}{2} \ \frac{m}{2} \ \frac{m}{2} \ \dots \ \frac{m}{2}}_{\frac{m}{2} \text{ elements}} \end{array} \right] \quad (8)$$

for $m > 2$, proof of equation (14) is found in [15].

III. FUNCTION APPROXIMATION

Any function $y(x) \in L^2(R)$ can be decomposed as

$$y(x) = \sum c_n h_n(x) \quad (9)$$

where the coefficients c_n are determined by

$$c_n = 2^j \int y(x) h_n(x) dx \quad (10)$$

where $n = 2^j + k$, $j \geq 0$, $0 \leq k < 2^j$. Specially

$$c_0 = \int y(x) dx \quad (11)$$

The series expansion of $y(x)$ contains an infinite terms. If $y(x)$ is piecewise constant by itself, or may be approximated as piecewise constant during each subinterval, then will be terminated at finite terms, that is

$$y(x) = \sum c_n h_n(x) = c_m^T h_m(x) \quad (12)$$

Where the coefficients c_m^T and the Haar function vector $h_m(x)$ are defined as

$$c_m^T = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{m-1}]$$

and $h_m(x) = [h_0(x), h_1(x), \dots, h_{m-1}(x)]$
 where 'T' means transpose and $m = 2^j$.

IV. METHOD OF SOLUTION OF FITZHUGH-NAGUMO EQUATION

Consider the FitzHugh-Nagumo equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + u(u - \alpha)(1 - u) \quad (13)$$

with the initial condition $u(x, 0) = f(x)$, $x \in [0, 1]$ and the boundary conditions $u(0, t) = g_0(t)$, $u(1, t) = g_1(t)$, $0 < t \leq T$

Let us divide the interval (0,1] into N equal parts of length $\Delta t = (0, 1]/N$ and denote $t_s = (s - 1)\Delta t$, $s = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

We assume that $u''(x, t)$ can be expanded in terms of Haar wavelets as formula

$$u''(x, t) = \sum c_s(n) h_n(x) = c_{(m)}^T h_{(m)}(x) \quad (14)$$

where \cdot and $'$ means differentiation with respect to t and x respectively, the row vector $c_{(m)}^T$ is constant in the subinterval $t \in (t_s, t_{s+1}]$

Integrating formula (14) with respect to t from t_s to t and twice with respect to x from 0 to x , we obtain

$$\dot{u}(x, t) = (t - t_s) c_{(m)}^T h_{(m)}(x) + u''(x, t_s) \quad (15)$$

$$u(x, t) = (t - t_s) c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x) + u(x, t_s) - u(0, t_s) + x[u'(0, t) - u'(0, t_s)] + u(0, t) \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{u}(x, t) = c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x) + x \dot{u}'(0, t) + \dot{u}(0, t) \quad (17)$$

By the boundary conditions, we obtain

$$u(0, t_s) = g_0(t_s), u(1, t_s) = g_1(t_s)$$

$$\dot{u}(0, t) = g'_0(t), \dot{u}(1, t) = g'_1(t)$$

Putting in formulae (16) and (17), we have

$$u'(0, t) - u'(0, t_s) = -(t - t_s) c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x) + g_1(t) - g_0(t) - g_1(t_s) + g_0(t_s) \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{u}'(0, t) = g'_1(t) - c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x) - g'_0(t) \quad (19)$$

Substituting formulae (18) and (19) into formulae (15)-(17), and discretizing the results by assuming $x \rightarrow x_l$, $t \rightarrow t_{s+1}$ we obtain

$$u''(x_l, t_{s+1}) = (t_{s+1} - t_s) c_{(m)}^T h_{(m)}(x_l) + u''(x_l, t_s) \quad (20)$$

$$u(x_l, t_{s+1}) = (t_{s+1} - t_s) c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x_l) + u(x_l, t_s) - g_0(t_s) + g_0(t_{s+1}) + x_l [-(t_{s+1} - t_s) c_{(m)}^T P_{(m)} f + g_1(t_{s+1}) - g_0(t_{s+1}) - g_1(t_s) + g_0(t_s)] \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{u}(x_l, t_{s+1}) = c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x) + g_1(t_{s+1}) + x_l [-c_{(m)}^T P_{(m)} f + g'_1(t_{s+1}) - g'_0(t_{s+1})] \quad (22)$$

Where the vector f is defined as

$$f = [1, \underbrace{0, \dots, 0}_{(m-1) \text{ elements}}]^T$$

In the following the scheme

$$\dot{u}(x_l, t_{s+1}) = u''(x_l, t_s + 1) + u(x_l, t_s + 1) \quad (23)$$

$$[u(x_l, t_s + 1) - \alpha][1 - u(x_l, t_s + 1)]$$

which leads us from the time layer t_s to t_{s+1} is used.

Substituting equations (20)-(23) into the equation (24), we gain

$$c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x_l) + x_l [-c_{(m)}^T P_{(m)} f + g'_1(t_{s+1}) - g'_0(t_{s+1})] + g'_0(t_{s+1}) = u''(x_l, t_{s+1}) + u(x_l, t_{s+1}) [u(x_l, t_{s+1}) - \alpha][1 - u(x_l, t_{s+1})] \quad (24)$$

From formula (24) the wavelet coefficients can be successively calculated.

V. TEST PROBLEM

Consider the following problem

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + u(u - \alpha)(1 - u) \quad (25)$$

with the initial condition $u(x, 0) = \lambda, x \in [0, 1]$ and the boundary conditions $u(0, t) = g_0(t), u(1, t) = g_1(t), 0 < t \leq T$

The Haar scheme is given by

$$c_{(m)}^T Q_{(m)}(x) h_{(m)}(x_i) + x_i [-c_{(m)}^T P_{(m)} \lambda + g_1'(t_{s+1}) - g_0'(t_{s+1})] + g_0'(t_{s+1}) = u''(x_i, t_{s+1}) + u(x_i, t_{s+1}) [u(x_i, t_{s+1}) - \alpha] [1 - u(x_i, t_{s+1})] \quad (26)$$

From formula (26) the wavelet coefficients can be successively calculated.

Using Adomian decomposition method, the exact solution in a closed form is given by

$$u(x, t) = 1/1 + e^{-\frac{\zeta}{\sqrt{2}}} \quad (27)$$

which is full agreement with the results in [15], where $\zeta = x + ct$ and $c = \sqrt{2}[\frac{1}{2} - \alpha]$

TABLE I
 COMPARISON OF EXACT AND HAAR SOLUTIONS FOR
 FITZHUGH-NAGUMO EQUATION AT $t = 0.48$ AND $m = 32$

x	Exact solution	Haar solution ($m = 32$)
0.1	0.52274	0.52246
0.2	0.55205	0.55197
0.3	0.58157	0.58135
0.4	0.61118	0.61099
0.5	0.64073	0.64057
0.6	0.67007	0.67045

Computer simulation was carried out in the cases $m=16$ and $m=32$, the computed results were compared with the exact solution, more accurate results can be obtained by using a larger m .

All the numerical experiments presented in this section were computed in double precision with some MATLAB codes on a personal computer System Vostro 1400 Processor x86 Family 6 Model 15 Stepping 13 Genuine Intel 1596 Mhz.

VI. CONCLUSION

The theoretical elegance of the Haar wavelet approach can be appreciated from the simple mathematical relations and their compact derivations and proofs. It has been well demonstrated that in applying the nice properties of Haar wavelets, the differential equations can be solved conveniently and accurately by using Haar wavelet method systematically. In comparison with existing numerical schemes used to solve the nonlinear parabolic equations, the scheme in this paper is an improvement over other methods in terms of accuracy. It is worth mentioning that Haar solution provides excellent results even for small values of (\cdot) . For larger values of (i.e., , , and), we can obtain the results closer to the real values. The Fitzhugh-Nagumo (FN) equation is a special case of the Burgers-Huxley equation. The Burgers-Huxley equation also has special cases where it reduces to the Burgers equation

and to the Newell-Whitehead equation. The main goal of this work is to apply the Haar wavelet method to the well-known Fitzhugh-Nagumo (FN) equation that appears in many scientific applications. The work also confirmed the power of the Haar wavelet method in handling nonlinear equations in general. This method can be easily extended to find the solution of all other non-linear parabolic equations. Another benefit of our method is that the scheme presented here, with some modifications, seems to be easily extended to solve model equations including more mechanical, physical or biophysical effects, such as nonlinear convection, reaction, linear diffusion and dispersion.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Abbasbandy, Soliton solutions for the Fitzhugh-Nagumo equation with the homotopy analysis method, Applied Mathematical Modelling 32 (2008) 2706-2714.
- [2] H.A. Abdusalam, Analytic and approximate solutions for Nagumo telegraph reaction diffusion equation, Appl. Math. and Comput. 157 (2004) 515-522.
- [3] M. Argentina, P. Coulet, V. Krinsky, Head-on collisions of waves in an excitable Fitzhugh-Nagumo system: a transition from wave annihilation to classical wave behavior, J. Theor. Biol. 205 (2000) 47.
- [4] D.G. Aronson, H.F. Weinberger, Multidimensional nonlinear diffusion arising in population genetics, Adv. Math. 30 (1978) 33-76.
- [5] C. Cattani, Haar wavelet spline, J. Interdisciplinary Math. 4 (2001) 35-47.
- [6] D.Y. Chen, Y. Gu, Cole-Hopf quotient and exact solutions of the generalized Fitzhugh-Nagumo equations, Acta Math. Sci. 19 (1) (1999) 7-14.
- [7] C.F. Chen, C.H. Hsiao, Haar wavelet method for solving lumped and distributed-parameter systems, IEEE Proc. Pt. D 144 (1) (1997) 87-94.
- [8] R. Fitzhugh, Impulse and physiological states in models of nerve membrane, Biophys. J. 1 (1961) 445-466.
- [9] P.-L. Gong, J.-X. Xu, S.-J. Hu, Resonance in a noise-driven excitable neuron model, Chaos Solitons Fract. 13 (2002) 885.
- [10] A. Haar Zur theorie der orthogonalen Funktionssysteme. Math. Annal 1910:69:331- 71.
- [11] G. Hariharan, K. Kannan, K.R. Sharma, Haar wavelet method for solving Fisher's equation, Appl. Math. and Comput. (2009)
- [12] G. Hariharan, K. Kannan, K.R. Sharma, Haar wavelet in estimating depth profile of soil temperature, Appl. Math. and Comput. (2009).
- [13] A.L. Hodgkin, A.F. Huxley, A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve, J. Physiol. 117 (1952) 500.
- [14] C.H. Hsiao, W.J. Wang, Haar wavelet approach to nonlinear stiff systems, Math. Comput. Simulat. 57, pp.347-353, 2001.
- [15] D.S. Jone, B.D. Sleeman, Differential Equations and Mathematical Biology, Chapman & Hall / CRC, New York, 2003.
- [16] T. Kawahara, M. Tanaka, Interaction of travelling fronts: an exact solution of a nonlinear diffusion equation, Phys. Lett. A 97 (1983) 311-314.
- [17] U. Lepik, Numerical solution of evolution equations by the Haar wavelet method, J. Appl. Math. Comput. 185 (2007) 695-704.
- [18] U. Lepik, Numerical solution of differential equations using Haar wavelets, Math. and Comp. Simulation 68(2005) 127-143.
- [19] U. Lepik, Application of the Haar wavelet transform to solving integral and differential Equations, Proc. Estonian Acad. Sci. Phys. Math., 2007, 56, 1, 28-46.
- [20] H. Li, Y. Guo, New exact solutions to the Fitzhugh-Nagumo equation, Appl. Math. and Comput. 180 (2006) 524-528.
- [21] D. Margerit, D. Barkley, Selection of twisted scroll waves in three-dimensional excitable media, Phys. Rev. Lett. 86 (1) (2001) 175.
- [22] J.S. Nagumo, S. Arimoto, S. Yoshizawa, An active pulse transmission line simulating nerve axon, Proc. IRE 50 (1962) 2061-2071.
- [23] M.C. Nucci, P.A. Clarkson, The nonclassical method is more general than the direct method for symmetry reductions: an example of the Fitzhugh-Nagumo equation, Phys. Lett. A 164 (1992) 49-56.
- [24] H.C. Rosu, O. Cornejo-Perez, Super symmetric pairing of kinks for polynomial nonlinearities, Phys. Rev. E 71 (2005) 1-13.
- [25] M. Shih, E. Momoniat, F.M. Mahomed, Approximate conditional symmetries and approximate solutions of the perturbed Fitzhugh-Nagumo equation, J. Math. Phys. 46 (2005) 023503.

- [26] A. Slavova, P. Zecca, CNN model for studying dynamics and travelling wave solutions of FitzHugh-Nagumo equation, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 151 (2003) 13-24.
- [27] A.M. Wazwaz, The tanh-coth method for solitons and kink solutions for nonlinear parabolic equations, *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 188 (2007) 1467.
- [28] M.P.Zorzano, L. Vazquez, Emergence of synchronous oscillations in neural networks excited by noise, *Physica D* 3078 (2003) 1.